

**A STUDY ON STUDENT PERCEPTION TOWARDS
PROFESSIONAL SOCIETY ACTIVITIES WITH REFERENCE TO
DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE,
PERAMBALUR**

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Abstract:

This paper deals with the evaluation on student perception towards professional society activities with reference to Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur

Introduction:

In 1996 recently established National Academy of Engineering (NAE) convened a symposium to determine what role it should play in engineering education. Participants also discussed what professional engineering societies are doing about engineering education (NAE 1966). Fifty-year later, the NAE is again asking the extent and nature of engineering societies contributions to improving the quality and effectiveness of engineering education in the united states. The emergence of professional engineering societies in the united states was a result of the technological revolution that began in the late 1800s. The massive expansion of rail and telegraph lines after 1870 allowed unprecedented movement of people and ideas. As Edwin Layton (2003) noted, the societies became a means for developing professional spirit among engineers; and as the sometimes adverse effects of rapid technological change became manifest they also became a means for expressing their members sense of social responsibility. In order to show you the most relevant results, we have omitted some entries very similar to the 0 already displayed. A professional association (also called a professional body, professional organization, or professional society) seeks to further a particular profession, the interests of individuals engaged in that profession and the public interest.

Review of Literature:

Bhave (2008) and chatrah (2008) have examined stress/anxiety in junior college youth and stress among high school students and medical students respectively and developed life skill programme to overcome these, Kenneth (2008) investigated the effect of life skill training on academic stress of standard tenth students and concluded that school is major contributor to students stress proper management of stress in adolescent is highly is highly essential for success in adulthood.

Morton (1993) studied grade 12 students participated in a 1-semester cooperative education program and were monitored using the personal skills map by Neslon & Law. Results indicate greater improvement in scores for the scales related to interpersonal skills than for those in the areas of career and life effectiveness skills (LKS).

Greenhil (2009) focused on how ongoing dialogue around 21st century knowledge and skills can be appropriately embedded in preparation and to guide the development of resources and services to support educator programs.

Hanefeld, Lunt, Smith, and Horsfall (2015) questioned who influences clients' decisions and found that in a case where an important decision needed to be made, people explore private and public networks and trusted social media recommendations. Besides that, networks help decide about the service provider. These findings indicate the power of social media in choosing various options, services, and solutions.

Lupton (2013) speaks about the contemporary "quantified self," the voluntary self-tracking and sharing of human body information phenomena. The researcher discusses technologies as an equal actant, which could become "friend" or "colleague" and could be continuously virtually reconstructed.

Scope of the Study:

- Advice on Policy
- Challenge / Competitions and Awards
- Curriculum Development
- Databases
- Industry Institute Interaction

- Institutional Development
- IT Education Standards and Leadership Development

Objectives of the Study:

- A Study on Student Perception Towards Professional Society Activities With Reference to Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur
- To analyze student involvement in professional society.
- To analyze the impartment and knowledge level among students.

Research Methodology:

Research is the process of systematic and in depth study or search of any particular topic, subject or area of investigation, backed by collection, compilation, Presentation and interpretation of relevant details or data. It is careful search or find out valuation facts, which would be useful for further application or utilization.

Research Design:

The researcher used Descriptive Research Design. Descriptive Research design means fact finding one. The Research used this research design to find out the fact of respondents attitude and opinion about student empowerment.

Sampling Design:

The Sampling type is Simple Random Sample which involves deliberating selection of particular units constituting a sample, which represents the universe, is used for conducting the study.

Sample Size:

Sample size denotes the number of sample selected for the study. They sample size for this study is fixed at 250 respondents.

Data Collection Method:

Data are the basic input to any decision making processing of data gives statistics of importance of study.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data

Primary Data:

Primary Data were collected through Questionnaire. The data which are collected a fresh for the first time and happen to be original in character.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square Test
- Correlation

Limitation of the Study:

- As opinions are dynamic the results of the based on these opinions are likely to differ in future.
- The result also depends on the integrity of the respondents in giving true and fair opinions and their level of knowledge in subject under study.
- In spite of the these opinions it is likely to provide some basic insights about the attitudes of the employees regarding the performance appraisal system measures taken by the company which may be used as bench marking for further study about this system in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering college

Show Satisfied With the Membership in Our College:

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents
1	Highly Satisfied	35
2	Satisfied	75
3	Neutral	60
4	Dissatisfied	45
5	Highly Dissatisfied	35
	Total	250

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
20	15	400	225	300
25	27	625	441	525
30	38	900	729	810
43	48	1225	1444	1330
47	51	1839	234	264
$\sum X=250$	$\sum Y=2250$	$\sum X^2=9978$	$\sum Y^2=1244$	$\sum XY=2500$

Chart 1: Show Satisfied with the Membership in our College

Interpretation:

From the above table shows that 14% of the respondents are highly satisfied,30%of the respondents are satisfied,24%of the respondents are neutral,18% of the respondents are dissatisfied and the finally 14%of the respondents are highly dissatisfied.

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between Aware about the library resource (x) and Satisfied with the resource of library (Y).

Suggestions:

- Most of the followings ideas were gathered from NSPE state and chapter leaders who wanted to share their chapter activity experiences.
- Meetings
- Continuing Education
- Outings, Tours
- Engineering Students
- Shaping policy
- Joint NSPE Members / Family Activities
- National Engineer’s Week

Conclusion:

Most researchers are members of professional societies. When these societies choose to support a particular policy, they convey the “voice” of the research enterprise with a unique degree of legitimacy. They now have the opportunity to raise that voice on behalf of interdisciplinary research and education: to broaden the interdisciplinary outlook of scientists, to recognize young interdisciplinary scientists of talent, and to facilitate the interdisciplinary strengths of their society.

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